

SECALE CEREALE L. CONTENT OF DRY SUBSTANCE IN MODERATE AND DRY CONDITIONS

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Abstract

Plants, in the process of photosynthesis, produce organic matter in inorganic substances, which are used for the growth, development, and reproduction of plants. One of the important results of the photosynthesis process is the indicator of dry matter formation. In our research, we determined the formation of dry matter and the rate of dry matter formation in the phases of development of rye varieties grown in the conditions of the Samarkand region under moderate and arid conditions.

Therefore, this article provides information on how much the dry matter mass of annual rye varieties changes under moderate and arid conditions, and the degree of influence of drought on this indicator.

Keywords: rye, phenological phases, dry matter, Vakhsh-116, Shalola, Savo, moisture, drought.

Abstract. This article provides information on the beneficial properties of the rye plant and its use in medicine and agriculture.

Keywords: rye, vitamins, amino acids, proteins, starch.

Introduction

Today, the importance of rye among grain crops is invaluable. In particular, in recent years, the demand for products made from rye flour has increased. Because bread made from rye flour is distinguished by its nutritional value and good taste. Therefore, measures are currently being taken to widely implement rye cultivation technology and cultivate drought-resistant rye varieties to obtain high yields [5;6].

Rye (*Secale cereale* L), which is closely related to wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), has been cultivated in Europe for more than 1000 BC and has several advantages over other grain crops [8].

Rye has been recognized as a drought-resistant grain crop due to its high physiological properties, and it has been established that its well-developed root system absorbs water very effectively. Therefore, the dry weight of rye roots

exceeds that of wheat and triticale. Moreover, rye consumes 20-30% less water per unit of dry matter than wheat [2;3].

Drought resistance and nutritional stress resistance are important components of yield stability, as rye is widely cultivated in poor, sandy soils. Compared to wheat, rye has much higher tolerance to abiotic stresses such as drought, nitrogen deficiency, and aluminum, zinc, sodium, and acidity[4].

Since rye grain is rich in energy and contains more digestible protein and total digestible nutrients than corn or barley grain, and contains more starch than barley, rye grain is increasingly used as nutritious feed for livestock on farms or by feed producers. Additionally, rye straw is considered a very nutritious feed for livestock [4;5;8].

It was established that even in arid conditions, several physiological properties of rye did not change significantly compared to other grain crops. In general, the impact of drought on rye varies from the molecular level to the morphological level. The impact of drought on rye is especially observed at phenological stages. For example, one of the first reactions to the effects of drought is the closure of leaf stomata. This leads to a disruption in the rate of photosynthesis and a significant decrease in carbon assimilation. Lower drought exposure reduces cell division, negatively impacting plant growth. If drought is observed during the phenological development of the plant, it leads to its early flowering and shortening of the grain filling period. Drought has resulted in a significant decrease in rye yields to varying degrees [1;2].

This drought, observed today in the world, has a serious impact on living organisms, including the plant world. As a result, the main productivity indicators of plants mainly lead to a decrease in yield and its quality. Due to the further deepening of scientific research aimed at reducing the negative impact of such a water shortage, as well as the revision of measures to preserve the lost crop, the assessment and substantiation of the physiological aspects of the impact of drought, research work carried out in this direction is considered as an important task [6;7;11].

Therefore, in recent years, a number of measures have been implemented in the territory of the republic to assess the impact of drought on plant varieties, to create drought-resistant plant varieties, and to improve the quantity and quality of the yield obtained from them.

Methods.

Field experiments.

Field experiments were conducted using the most common and tested methods in an environment with optimal and arid transpiration intensity of rye varieties.

The research was conducted at the "Ulug' Baraka" farm in the Jomboy district of the Samarkand region.

The amount of dry matter was determined by drying in a drying cabinet to a constant mass according to the method of L.G.Tretyakov, A.S.Sulaymonov [10].

In our studies, winter rye seeds were sown in rows (with a row spacing of 15 cm), in narrow rows (with a row spacing of 7.5 cm), and in double rows using coordinated methods. Seeds were sown to an average depth of 4-5 cm. Rye varieties were grown in moderate and limited humidity conditions. In this case, fungicides and pepticides were used to prevent various harmful plant diseases.

Soil and climatic conditions

The climatic conditions of the experimental area are distinguished by their specificity. The hottest period occurs in July and the coldest in January. In general, the climate is strongly continental, with air temperatures rising to +42+43°C in summer and dropping to -22-23°C in winter. Warm and dry summers are characterized by abundant precipitation in spring, repeated hot and cold air in autumn, and cold winters.

The amount of precipitation varies significantly by month. At the same time, the lowest precipitation falls mainly in July-August.

The soils of the region consist of typical sierozems. The humus content in the soil is low, not exceeding 1%.

In our experiment, 3 varieties of winter rye (*S. cereale* L.), namely "Vakhsh-116," "Shalola," and "Savo" were used. These varieties were grown in moderate and limited humidity conditions.

Obtained results and their analysis

Plants, in the process of photosynthesis, produce organic matter in inorganic substances, which are used for the growth, development, and reproduction of plants. One of the important results of the photosynthesis process is the indicator of dry matter formation.

Plant growth, development, yield indicators, and photosynthetic activity are inextricably linked to their water availability.

Sufficient water in plants influences the high level of all physiological processes occurring in them. Insufficient water leads to the disruption of all processes occurring in the plant.

In our research, we determined the formation of dry matter in the

developmental phases of rye varieties grown in the conditions of the Samarkand region in moderate and arid conditions, and the data obtained as a result of the research were as follows.

Figure 1. Accumulation of dry matter in the developmental phases of rye varieties under moderate conditions (g/plant).

According to the above data, it was established that in rye varieties growing in moderate conditions, the dry matter content in the tillering phase ranged from 2.9 g/plant to 3.3 g/plant. The formation of dry matter in rye varieties was observed most intensively in the tubing phase. In this phase, the dry matter content in the Vakhsh-116 variety was 17.6 g/plant, in the Shalola variety 17.9 g/plant, and in the Savo variety 16.1 g/plant. In this phase, the amount of dry matter in the Vakhsh-116 variety increased by 14.3 g, in the Shalola variety by 14.4 g, and in the Savo variety by 13.2 g.

In the heading phase, the total dry matter content in rye varieties ranged from 22.2 g/plant to 27.8 g/plant. In the flowering phase, a further increase in the total dry matter content of the varieties was observed, ranging from 29.8 g/plant to 33.8 g/plant. It was found that during the milk and wax ripeness phases, the dry matter content of the varieties decreases. During the milk ripening phase, the accumulation of dry matter was 33.1 g, 35.6 g, and 30.3 g, respectively. It was established that by the wax ripening phase, the leaf surface area in plants decreases, and the rate of dry matter formation decreases due to the drying and falling of leaves. In this phase, the rate of dry matter formation increased by 1.4 g in the Vakhsh-116 variety, 2.1 g in the Shalola variety, and 1.3 g in the Savo variety.

It was found that the accumulation of dry matter in rye varieties decreased

in arid conditions compared to temperate conditions.

Based on the data presented in Figure 2, it was established that the formation of dry matter in rye varieties during the tillering phase ranges from 2.8 g to 3.5 g. In the tubing phase, the rate of dry matter formation changed to 11.2>11.4>11.5 g. In subsequent phases, a decrease in the rate of dry matter formation was observed. In the heading phase, the rate of dry matter formation was 7.1 g, 7.6 g, 6.5 g, respectively. In the flowering phase, it was found that this indicator decreased further and was in the range of 5.1>6.1>6.7. It has been substantiated that the rate of dry matter formation decreases significantly compared to other phases due to the decrease in the leaf surface area of plants by the grain ripening phase and the shedding of leaves.

Figure 2. Accumulation of dry matter in the developmental phases of rye varieties under arid conditions (g/plant).

In general, in our studies, it was established that the level of water content in the soil affects the formation of total organic matter in rye varieties. At the end of the growing season, the highest accumulation of organic matter was observed in the Shalola variety even in moderate and arid conditions, and the relatively low amount of organic matter was observed in the Savo variety.

Conclusion: Based on the above data, it can be concluded that the accumulation of organic matter in rye varieties in moderate conditions is higher than in arid conditions. The rate of dry matter formation was found to be in the tubing phase under both conditions.

Limited moisture content led to a significant decrease in the accumulation of dry matter. Consequently, the drought caused a decrease in the most important physiological indicators of rye varieties.

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